

HINDRANCE TO EFFECTIVE ENGLISH SPEAKING AT HIGHER SECONDARY LEVEL: A CASE STUDY ON THE COLLEGES OF DHAKA CITY IN BANGLADESH			Linguistics
		Keywords: Competency, Dhaka, effective English speaking, higher secondary level, hindrance.	
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Abstract			
<p>The paper aims at investigating the prevailing barriers that the learners of higher secondary level in Dhaka city encounter in speaking English effectively in their classrooms. It reconnoitres the challenges that prevail in the teaching-learning environment and impede rehearsing English speaking inside the classroom. English has been inescapably used in everyday life in this period of intense global competition. But for various reasons, students in higher secondary level often struggle to develop adequate speaking skills. And these obstacles affect in their upcoming higher study, going abroad as well as in their future career. This study aims to locate the hindrances that most of the students of the level face in speaking English fluently in the classroom. A systematic study is conducted using a quantitative approach, and a questionnaire is used to obtain data. The findings accentuate the unreachability of logistic, managerial, and administrative amenities; unapproachability of pertinent teaching-learning techniques, methods and approaches, inaccessibility of reciprocated and accommodating setting that reinforce the core impediments in teaching-learning English speaking at higher secondary stage. This paper pinpoints all those problems and presents probable recommendations to develop English speaking competency. Future scholars will benefit from this study's insights as they investigate the difficulties faced by English language learners in Bangladesh.</p>			

1. INTRODUCTION

In Bangladesh, English is taught as a compulsory subject from primary to the higher secondary level. Nonetheless, most of the students of this higher secondary stage are not fluent in speaking. This study mainly explores which hindrances are faced by the students of higher secondary level of different colleges under Dhaka city and how those obstacles can be overcome. The study puts forward the following questions:

- a) What are the main difficulties that are faced by the higher secondary level students of different colleges in Dhaka city?
- b) Why are most of the students of this level inefficient in speaking fluently?
- c) How suitable is the existing curriculum of the secondary and higher secondary levels for developing conversational skill?
- d) How much effective is the current testing system for evaluating students' speaking skill appropriately?

Lack of teaching tools, the teaching environment, and lack of proper testing system are the main barriers to speaking skills at higher secondary level. Brown & Yule (1988) mention that language has two functions - transferring information (transactional function) and maintaining social relationships (interactional function). Liu and Jackson (2008) found that the lack of vocabulary was regarded as a main hindrance to spoken communication by English learners.

In the present study, inadequate vocabulary is also reported as a prevalent concern among the students although they are exposed to range of words and phrases at this stage. But when it comes to speaking, these words and phrases never come to their mind, so the expression they deliver intended meaning precisely. This is also contributed to a lack of fluency in their speech.

Brown (2007) found that teacher's negative discourse regarding student's performance on assignment or exams can affect students' motivation and willingness to communicate. Hasan in the project (2004) found that about 82% of rural and urban college students complain that English is not sufficiently used in the class; with an average 68% of teachers admitting that they do not arrange the practice of the four skills (L. S. R and W) of English language in the classroom.

Kishore (1998) found that traditional techniques of English language teaching in Bangladesh are translation, mother tongue passage are given to the examinee to be translated into the foreign language. Essays; requiring the examinees to write long or short essays as techniques of testing language ability has been practiced for ages. Dictation has also been a favourite device with traditionalist, both as a teaching and testing device. Here also mentions that there are two main types of test items, which can be further subdivided. Open ended, selective type, multiple facers, mating type, rearrangement type, and supply type. For speaking skills tests; recognition of sounds can also be tested with the help of pictures, pronunciation testing should require the learner to speak in everyday situations, stress can be tasted, to start with, with those words which are identical in segmental sounds and differ only on stress, grammatical structures with normal fluency, vocabulary can be easily tested by means of picture fluency can be tested by giving some topic of common interest and making the examinees participate in conversation with the examiner.

Zhao (2001) mentions about the important of speaking testing and developing procedure. In the classroom students can practices three minutes presentation, discussion, question and answer test may play an active role. For this environment is necessary, arrangement is necessary, methods are important for evaluating speaking. Hasan (2004) has focused social stratification & proficiency in English, Language teaching theories & their implication and a review of testing scheme & evaluation policy of English language teaching in Bangladesh. Students are still far away from the expected level of proficiency. Inconsistencies were mostly found at the classroom implementation level. The teacher of English somehow failed to adhere to an appropriate methodology to carry out teaching and learning.

Kiany (1997) mentions that extraversion may not help in developing either linguistic skills or even communicative skills in such an Iranian EFL Situation where there is no exposure to English and where non-communicative teaching methods are used in English classes. This preliminary research led to the main study which includes three different sub samples - no English exposure, exposure to English only in classes, and exposure to the language in a natural English - Speaking environment - as well as a much wider variety of measurements of English proficiency. The students also have hardly any opportunity to use English in their real life. They have hardly any supplementary reading materials to reinforce their knowledge and skills they learn from their textbooks. Textbooks are, therefore, the only means for teaching and learning English. So, the English language teaching and learning situation in Bangladesh is an unfavourable one. In such an unfavourable situation, where textbooks are the only materials easily available, they (textbooks) should be so developed as to help both teachers and students with sufficient examples and a variety of materials for practice in communicative use of language.

McCarty (2009) has mentioned many criteria for evaluating English speaking are possible, and there are as many ways as possible to prioritize them. Especially when the parties involved are from different cultures, these criteria cannot be taken for granted as mutually understood and agreed upon. The main purpose for the JTE and ALT to discuss criteria and clarify their priorities to the students is to ensure fairness in grading. Yet in learning what constitutes effective speaking, particularly to native speakers of English, students also gain a clearer picture of where their speaking practice is aimed, and they can better simulate English speaking as an effective form of international communication.

Zafor (2010) expresses that Communicative English, one of the major objectives of which is to emphasize on speaking skill, was introduced in the national curriculum more than a decade ago in order to enhance our students' overall skills, especially speaking skill, that were neglected in our curriculum since independence. But have we achieved any level of success and are we on the right track to achieve our objectives? The answer is a big 'no.' Barman, Sultana and Basu(2006) that Bangladesh is one of the few countries of the world where teachers can start teaching without any formal training. Bangladesh, of course, is a country with limited resources and economic constraints that inevitably hamper the efforts and motivation of local ELT practitioners. They point out some factors that the teachers face in implementing the principles of communicative language teaching at a higher secondary level. The factors are infrastructural limitations, cultural conflicts, seating arrangement in class- room, lack of standard testing system etc.

Rahman (2010) advocates that though the national curriculum and syllabus have underscored the need for developing all the four English skills namely listening, speaking, reading and writing, the existing examination system is heavily based on writing and reading skills only. Unfortunately, the two important skills, listening and speaking are being completely left out in the English examination system. As a result, the teachers and students do not feel encouraged to teach and learn these two skills in the classroom. But ELTIP is working to ensure balanced and

integrated development of all the four skills among the learners. However as there are no marks allocated for speaking and listening skills in the examination system, students are not motivated to practice speaking and listening. In any internal as well as public examination on English there must be a component on speaking and listening and at least 10 to 20% of the total marks can be allocated for these two skills. Students will have to face a viva board where they will be asked to speak in English. If this system of oral testing will be incorporated in all tests from class 6 to 12 the learners will get the avenues to make himself confident as well as fluent in English after completing HSC/Alim.

Thus, this study investigates the actual condition of teaching, testing and the problems they really face at the higher secondary and how we can overcome these barriers.

This research is an authentic scenario of the higher secondary learners in Dhaka city, Bangladesh. The problems of learners that they face for speaking fluently have been investigated in this research. This is a potential source of study for the stakeholders, policy makers, researchers, teachers, and trainers, who want to carry out further research on language learning as well as basic skills of English. The result of this paper may be the basis to investigate the total condition of secondary level students of the country. Importantly, the Ministry of Education, National Curriculum and Textbook Board (NCTB), and different educational institutions would benefit from this study.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Study design

This is a quantitative study and descriptive in nature. The empirical data have been obtained by the questionnaire survey. Then, they are identified, classified, interpreted, analysed, and presented. For the study, four colleges under Dhaka North City Corporation were selected- Rajuk Uttara Model College (RUMC), Civil Aviation School and College, Uttara High School and College and Milestone College in a systematic manner.

2.2. Population (Respondents) of the Study

The respondents of this research were the higher secondary level learners in Dhaka city area by random sampling approach.

2.3. Sampling size

Total 100 respondents were taken. 25 students from each school from three groups – Science, Arts and Business Studies participated. They were asked questions or statements about their present speaking performance, their classroom environment, teachers' cooperation and performance, their opinion about the contribution of HSC syllabus and textbooks to develop conversational skill and so on.

2.4. Sources of Data

This study is mainly based on primary data which were collected through a survey in October 2022 and secondary data were from many books, reports, articles, papers, journals and other published documents related to speaking skills for the basic and relevant information of the study.

2.5. Procedure

The survey was conducted directly going to the respondents and the duration of the survey was one week. They took around 8-10 minutes to answer the questions.

2.6. Data analysis framework

Research Tools	Approach	Sample Size	Sampling Procedure	Mode of Analysis	Nature of Analysis
Questionnaire	Quantitative	100	Random	Statistical Analysis (%)	Descriptive

2.7. Analyses of the findings

1. *Effective speaking skill refers to a person's ability to speak a language with maximum accuracy, interaction, and fluency.*

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Agree	42	42%
Disagree	2	2%
Strongly agree	50	50%
Strongly disagree	1	1%
Neutral	5	5%
Total Respondent	100	100%

Effective speaking ability is a person's capacity to speak a language in order to communicate with others. Effective speaking skill refers to a person's ability to speak a language with maximal precision and fluency, as defined by the first question of the questionnaire. The results of the study indicate that 50% of students strongly agree, 42% agree, while just 1% strongly disagrees, and 5% do not express any opinion.

2. I can speak English.

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Fluently	6	6%
Moderately	44	44%
Little	30	30%
Very Little	15	15%
Unable	5	5%
Total Respondent	100	100%

This question pertains to the participants' communication skills. Here, respondents were asked to identify their degree of English proficiency in interpersonal communication. As a consequence, 44% of respondents can speak English with a moderate level of proficiency, while just 6% can speak it well. On the other side, 30% of respondents speak English minimally, and 15% speak English very little. Also regrettable is the fact that 5% of respondents cannot speak English and are unable to communicate with others using the language.

3. How often do you speak in English with your teachers?

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Always	2	2%
Sometimes	6	6%
Rarely	38	38%
Often	24	24%
Never	30	30%
Total Respondent	100	100%

The table and graph reveal that just 2% of respondents always talk English with their instructors, 6% of respondents sometimes speak English with their teachers, 38% of respondents sometimes speak English with their teachers, and 30% of students never speak English with their faculty members. It is quite disappointing that so few pupils speak English, when the majority of students should speak English.

4. How often do you speak in English with your classmates?

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Always	0	0%
Sometimes	5	5%
Rarely	55	55%
Often	15	15%
Never	25	25%
Total Respondent	100	100%

Conversation in practical life, context furnishes speaking skill properly. The important fact is that most of the time in Bangladesh particularly people circumvent of using English in everyday life as English is the foreign language here. In case of students, though they are bound to talk in English with the teacher in classes sometimes; they remain reluctant to talk with mates, peers, friends frequently. The result of the data analysis displays that 25% respondents never speak English with their classmates; a large percentage (55%) respondents rarely speak. On the other hand, only 5% respondents speak sometimes, 15% respondents speak often and none speaks English always.

5. Classroom provides students with a proper atmosphere to practise speaking skill.

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Agree	48	48%
Disagree	35	35%
Strongly agree	4	4%
Strongly disagree	6	6%
Neutral	7	7%
Total Respondent	100	100%

A classroom convenient circumstance helps to test properly. Sufficient space, moderate class size, adequate lighting and a room with acoustics that is neither too hot nor too cold are important for teaching. Most important things for the successful teaching and learning are fewertangible conditions, plenty of opportunities for learners to practise in class and an atmosphere in which they feel motivated to learn. The teaching arrangement should be organised in such a way that the learners would be enthusiastic in the activities and interactionswhich take place in the classroomwithout constraints. However, one of the questions of study was whether the classroom provides students with a congenial atmosphere to practise speaking skill or not.

This analysis shows that though 48% respondents agree with the statement, only 4% respondents strongly agree, 35% respondents disagree with the statement, 6% of them strongly disagree, and only 7% of them are neutral.

6. How often does your teacher use English in the classroom?

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Always	15	15%
Sometimes	60	60%
Rarely	4	4%
Often	20	20%
Never	1	1%
Total Respondent	100	100%

To develop English speaking, learners are supposed to be involved in speaking in the classroom to integrate their conversational skill through practising by role play, group discussion, talk show etc. Most importantly, teachers can expedite it for students to talk in English with them. Though 1% respondents answer that their teachers never speak in the classroom, more than half (60%) of respondents express their opinion on the option of sometimes. Again, 4% respondents speak rarely but 20% respondents think that their teacher speaks often. Further, only 15% respondents affirm that their teacher always speaks English in the class.

7. How much do your teachers encourage you to speak in English?

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Always	51	51%
Sometimes	30	30%
Rarely	6	6%
Often	13	13%
Never	0	0%
Total Respondent	100	100%

Instructors or teachers can motivate the learners to learn English. Indeed, they can remove students' fear and teach them in an interesting way. The table and figure show that 51% of respondents claim that their teachers always encourage them to speak in English inside and outside the class; 30% respondents assert that their teachers sometimes encourage them to speak in English. Only 6% respondents answer for the option of rarely where 13% respondents contend for the choice of often. It is a very positive sign that all of the teachers encourage the respondents to speak in English. Thus, the percentage for never option is zero.

8. All the four language skills of your syllabus are needed to give importance equally.

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Agree	45	45%
Disagree	6	6%
Strongly agree	40	40%
Strongly disagree	0	0%
Neutral	9	9%
Total Respondent	100	100%

The textbook that is prescribed by NCTB for the higher secondary level is not designed to emphasis on the four skills equally. Only reading and writing skills are practised in the classroom in most of the time. The table and figure show that about 45% of the whole respondents agree that all the four skills are obligatory to be taught effectively in Bangladesh including 40% respondents strongly agree. Side by side, 6% of them disagree. None of them strongly disagree and 9% respondents remain neutral.

9. Students know IPA symbols and can transcribe English words phonemically.

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Agree	3	3%
Disagree	66	66%
Strongly agree	1	1%
Strongly disagree	24	24%
Neutral	6	6%
Total Respondent	100	100%

International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) is essential for transcribing sounds that occur in a language, whether oral or sign. If the learners know these symbols, they would be able to transcribe English words phonemically. This question of the questionnaire was whether the student knows the IPA Symbols and transcribes English words phonemically or not. The table and figure show that 3% respondents agree wherever 66% respondents disagree but only 1% respondents strongly agree, 24% respondents strongly disagree and 6% respondents remain neutral that they are familiar with IPA symbols and transcription.

10. Students have enough knowledge about speech sounds.

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Agree	8	8%
Disagree	60	60%
Strongly agree	2	2%
Strongly disagree	20	20%
Neutral	10	10%
Total Respondent	100	100%

Speech sounds help the learners to acquire English pronunciation correctly through simulation and practice. If the learners can disinter the speech sound; they can ameliorate the intonation, stress, rhythm of their pronunciation of any language. The table and figure show that only 8% respondents agree that they have enough knowledge about it where more than half of the respondents (60%) disagree. Besides, 2% respondents strongly agree, 20% respondents strongly disagree, and 10% respondents are natural about the information that they have good command on the ornaments of speech sounds like stress, intonation, and rhythm.

11. Does your teacher take any test to check your speaking skill?

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Always	22	22%
Sometimes	56	56%
Rarely	6	6%
Often	16	16%
Never	2	2%
Total Respondent	100	100%

In Bangladesh, testing methods of English in HSC level only focus on reading and writing without any mark allocation for listening and speaking tests. Here one hundred marks are designed for English First Paper by dividing into three parts. Part A includes two reading comprehensions and there are four questions on each comprehension. Each question is of five marks. There are two questions on vocabulary in part B and each question contains ten marks. In Part C, there are 3 questions like a substitution table of twelve marks, a rearrangement of fourteen marks and a paragraph of fourteen marks. Again, a test of one hundred marks is allocated for the English second paper which aims at testing grammatical and writing skills of the learners. There are two parts in this question paper. Part A includes eight grammatical questions each contains five marks where part B includes questions on writing skill i.e., letter, application, dialogue, and composition writing. Thus, the learners face various obstacles on the way to speak effectively.

The seventh question of the designed questionnaire was whether the current testing system for evaluating students' speaking skill is appropriate or not. The table and figure show that about 8% respondents agree, 60% respondents disagree, 2% respondents strongly agree, 20% respondents strongly disagree and 10% respondents are neutral about the information that the current testing methods are sufficient to assess student speaking ability.

12. The current testing system for evaluating students' speaking skill is the appropriate one.

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Agree	12	12%
Disagree	44	44%
Strongly agree	8	8%
Strongly disagree	26	26%
Neutral	10	10%
Total Respondent	100	100%

In Bangladesh, with the exclusion of the speaking test, only partial assessment forms on the basis of grammar-translation oriented tests never bring the equal result as skill-focused assessment occurred in English language assessment. Amin and Greenwood et al. (2018) prolong that the current national examination system is not consistent with the curriculum goals and objectives. 12% respondents agree that the current testing system for evaluating students' speaking skill is the appropriate one, 44% respondents disagree, 8% respondents strongly agree but 26% respondents strongly disagree, and 10% respondents are neutral about the information that the current testing system for evaluating students' speaking skill is the appropriate one.

13. The existing syllabus is helping the learners to improve their speaking skill.

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Agree	11	11%
Disagree	30	30%
Strongly agree	2	2%
Strongly disagree	45	45%
Neutral	12	12%
Total Respondent	100	100%

This question of the research questionnaire was whether the current syllabus for higher secondary level gives emphasis on speaking skill with other three skills or not. The figure shows that about 20% respondents agree that the existing syllabus is helping the learners to improve their speaking skill. All the same 35% respondents disagree and 3% of all respondents strongly agree.

Furthermore, 27% respondents strongly disagree yet 15% of them remain neutral about the information that the current syllabus for higher secondary level gives emphasis on speaking skill with other three skills.

14. *The textbooks in the HSC are not sufficient for developing speaking skills.*

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Agree	20	20%
Disagree	35	35%
Strongly agree	3	3%
Strongly disagree	27	27%
Neutral	15	15%
Total Respondent	100	100%

The materials and content emulate indispensable function in teaching and learning of a language. On account of that the textbooks in the HSC level are highly needed to consider like how sufficient and efficient they are for developing learners' speaking skills. The respondents were asked to opine with the statement that the textbooks in the HSC are not sufficient for developing English skill. 3% respondents strongly agree with the statement that the textbooks are not sufficient for developing students' speaking skill. Again, 35% respondents agree with the proclamation where 15% respondents are neutral and 35% respondents disagree. Additionally, 27% strongly disagree with the statement.

15. *What are the main reasons for the lack of competency in English?*

Reponses	Number of Respondent	Percent
Nervousness	45	45%
Lack of practice	10	10%
Lack of proper words	27	27%
Lack of teachers' cooperation	3	3%
Syllabus does not emphasize	15	15%
Unfavorable Environment	8	8%
Total Respondent	100	100%

The aim of the question is to find out the general causes of students' inadequacy in English in the higher secondary level. The table and figure show that among all the participants 45% respondents think that nervousness is the main reason for lacking competence in English. Then, 10% respondents observe that lack of practice makes students inefficient in speaking. Further, 27% of students face a lack of proper words.

Teachers' cooperation is important in language class, but 3% respondents are coming unstuck in speaking for instructors' non-cooperative attitude. Then, 15% respondents believe that the HSC syllabus does not emphasise speaking properly on speaking. Again, 8% of total respondents cannot do well in speaking because of the lack of a favourable environment.

3. DISCUSSION

Luoma (2004) defined speaking as an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing, receiving and processing information (p.2). Speaking or conversation means a "multifaceted activity" (Richards, 1990). It is a matter of great concern that most second language learners, especially students of higher secondary level, feel the necessity of effective communication skill, but they are unable to communicate properly. They face a number of hindrances in the ways of developing speaking skill.

The result of the survey shows that the higher secondary level of the testing system for evaluating students' speaking ability is not appropriate. Here only written tests are emphasised. Only few students at these colleges refer to viva voce, interview, presentation and other oral tests. The major focus in the English class is on the two basic skills namely reading and writing. Little or no systematic attention is paid to speaking and listening.

It is a matter of sorrow that no college has a language laboratory and modern equipment for practising oral skills. They depend on only a sound speaker. In most of the colleges visual aids are not used. Thus, students cannot get the opportunity to understand the native speakers' pronunciation, organ of speech, production of sounds, phonetics and phonological transcription, etc.

Regular and frequent practice enables a person to have mastery over speaking. In this case, students need to converse with their teachers and classmates in English. Students hardly practise it. Even so, several students never speak English with their peers. Such a phobia for speaking on the part of students reduces their ability.

English skill is the interference of mother tongue. In the case of higher secondary level, the learners try to transfer different elements from their mother tongue to English. But most of the time they cannot speak spontaneous English though they speak their mother tongue Bangla naturally. Again, they mix both Bangla and English, popularly known as Banglish. But Bangla is even spoken in the English classroom, and it hampers their English learning.

The existing syllabus at higher secondary level prescribed by the NCTB is not suitable to develop speaking proficiency. HSC syllabuses seem to be less effective in developing communicative competence. It is not consistent with the Communicative Language Teaching Method. English first paper of HSC level some contents follow this method but the second paper does not. This only includes grammatical and written items.

It is a matter of hope that CLTA (Communicative Language Teaching Approach) has been introduced more constructively, but still dialogue making and other conversations are memorised.

The textbooks instruct the teachers for natural and contextual conversation such as situational talk, greetings, dialogue making, pair work etc. But they are followed neither by our teachers nor our students. The objectives of the textbooks are to enable the students to use the most common form of expression of the language freely and spontaneously. Sometimes students are forced to memorise because they need to pass in the examination, and they can do it without much effort and even their minds reside elsewhere. Again, for time limitation teachers arrange traditional types of questions which are not indeed proper for the speaking test. Our public examinations fail to put equal emphasis on all the four language skills. Even, questions in the public examinations are set on reading and writing but listening and speaking are excluded.

Further, higher secondary level students do not have good command on suprasegmental features of English language such as stress, intonation, rhythm etc. Most of the students do not have enough knowledge about English speech sounds and do not any idea about IPA symbols and transcription of it.

Consequently, students fail to internalise the necessary amount of vocabulary and try to memorise vocabulary without any reference of context and when they are needed, they can hardly use those properly which is an obstacle to fluent speaking.

In Bangladesh, people trying to speak English are not cordially appreciated; rather they are scorned and laughed at. For this reason, Bangladeshi EFL learners, basically higher secondary level students, do not find their environment congenial to the development of the speaking skill. Few students feel shy and fear that their local dialects affect their pronunciation. Again, some female students feel uncomfortable speaking in front of male students' cultural and gender barriers when they try to speak in English. But, for developing speaking skill, a favourable environment is needed, where a student can practise his or her conversation without any hesitation or shyness rather confidently.

In addition, many college teachers are not concerned about their responsibility and act as rulers over the students. Such kind of non-cooperation on the part of teachers highly contributes to the lack of competency in conversational skill in English.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

To overcome the obstacles to effective speaking skill at higher secondary level in Bangladesh the following suggestions can be taken into consideration: Students in the English class will not learn to speak fluently merely by hearing speech although this is important in familiarising them with the acceptable forms of language. Indeed, with spontaneity grammatical

correctness is also important. For speaking tests only viva voce is not enough. Students always concentrate on the items necessary for passing and getting a good grade in the examinations.

Rather, they avoid focusing on oral skills and other items though they are very essential in real life situations. The majority of study participants agreed that all four skills of the English language must be given equal weight. If our public examinations include oral communication, the situation may soon change. The testing system should be planned in such a way that students' command of the language can properly be judged. It is appropriate to give speaking and listening skills some credit. To help students overcome their challenges in developing effective speaking skills, active participation in the classroom, viva voce, debate, group discussions, presentations, or speaking on a particular topic can be more beneficial than a written test.

The existing HSC syllabus should be modified. It must be introduced in accordance with the demand of the Communicative Language Teaching Method. No method can bring output unless it is implemented completely. Furthermore, the teachers must be conscious so that they follow the current teaching method completely, not partially. In a language lesson, the teacher should play the role of a facilitator. Teachers should encourage students to speak English in conversational classes. He or she should be able to speak English in order to help the learners learn the language. Besides, teachers in the English speaking class should find themselves talking less and listening more and becoming active facilitators of their students' learning. Teachers should be cooperative to arrange situations so that students will be bound to talk in English at least in the classroom.

How to design the study materials and teach those effectively in the class is another important factor. Teaching items can be presented in an interesting way. Instead of teaching the rules of grammar by using sentences in isolation, those can be contextualised. Again, only grammar cannot help to express thoughts. But through vocabulary, one can express thoughts and communicate with others. Thus, the syllabus should be more focused on the contextual use of vocabulary. Teachers should teach through the real life situation.

In order to overcome the obstacles to excellent speaking ability, students require extensive practice. In a foreign nation, students are surrounded by native speakers. Expression and conversation around them strike their ears continuously. Thus, they can internalise skill without conscious effort. This constant hearing from native speakers is missing in a country like ours. Hence, they must converse and practise themselves.

The concept of supra-segmental features of English such as stress, intonation, rhythm, speech sounds, IPA symbols and phonetic transcription etc. can be added to text books in order to be proficient in speaking. Most of the teachers always keep the students under constant pressure for completing the prescribed syllabus that contains only Reading and Writing but there is no involvement of speaking skill. It is one of the major barriers to effective speaking skill. Teachers can make students engage in different situations like role play like short drama, pair works like

dialogue practising, poem recitation instead of writing, etc so that learners can get opportunity to be involved in speaking.

The use of multimedia materials in the present age can be fruitful for developing speaking skill. In the traditional classrooms, objects, pictures, actions, gestures etc. are used for language teaching. In recent years, the availability of film strips, slides, films, and tapes has made their use possible. The image accompanied by a voice is highly beneficial for developing speaking skills. College teachers must be well equipped and trained before starting teaching. Speaking relates to listening and so students should listen to English news, discussions and dialogues of native speakers as part of developing speaking skill. Students should overcome their fears and timidity, since they will only result in failure in language acquisition.

5. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Due to scheduling constraints, the study is just looking at students' perspectives; teacher interviews have not been done. The students who participated in the data collection came from four separate institutions in Dhaka, but they nonetheless serve as a representative sample of all Bangladeshi students. It is possible that some respondents did not really disclose their level of skill. When asked about the classroom atmosphere and teachers' performance, they were also asked whether they would feel threatened if their teachers learned the results. Some students had no experience conducting research, thus they perceived the survey as a time waster. The only skill discussed in this study is speaking.

6. CONCLUSION

To the end, the effective English speaking skill has become crucial to express oneself and to extend the connectivity to global networks. The ultimate result of this survey is that most of the students face the barriers like the interference of mother tongue, fossilisation, anxiety, Emotional Barrier (shyness), Cultural Barrier (local accent), lack of practice, vocabulary, immersion, student-teacher interaction, Physical Barrier (environment noise), Attitude Barrier (lack of motivation), Psychological Barrier (consciousness, emotions), etc. In these circumstances, conversational competence in English students must be improved from the initial stage. The higher secondary level is the most tactful-transit stage of the educational system of Bangladesh. After passing this level students enter into higher study in the country or overseas. If they cannot develop their basic skills of language, personal communication, and interaction, at this level, they become unable to succeed in higher education and career most of the time. This paper puts a way for future researchers to investigate the effects of hindrance in speaking like psychological, perceptual, and so on. Additionally, this study emphasizes the shortcomings of the speaking testing system in Bangladesh, lack of proper content in textbooks for practicing speaking, and the requirement for syllabus modification, such as adding English speaking courses to the current syllabus, which can assist the authorities of our educational system in rethinking it.

Author's contribution

D. Dilshad made a significant contribution to the article's concept, design and empirical survey. S.S. Ahmed contributed to the intellectual and theoretical analysis, and interpretation of findings and M. S. Islam did the initial draft work, as well as the final proofreading and editing.

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Conflict of interest

There is no potential conflict of interest regarding the publication of this work, as declared by the authors. In addition, the authors have witnessed all ethical concerns, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publishing and/or submission, and redundancy.

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